

Physicochemical and antimicrobial studies on nickel(II) and copper(II) Schiff base complexes derived from 2-furfuraldehyde

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Complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with Schiff bases, furfurylideneisoniazide (FIZ), viz. [Ni(FIZ)₂]Cl₂ (1) and [Cu(FIZ)₂]Cl₂ (2), furfurylidene-4-aminoantipyrine (FAAP), viz. [Ni(FAAP)₂(H₂O)₂]Cl₂ (3) and [Cu(FAAP)Cl₂]H₂O (4) and furfurylidene-2-aminopyridine (FAP), viz. [Ni(FAP)₂]Cl₂·2H₂O (5) and [Cu(FAP)₂]Cl₂·H₂O (6) have been synthesised. Coordination of azomethine nitrogen in the Schiff base to the metal has been proposed. Ligand field parameters for complexes 2 and 3 and esr parameters for 2 have been evaluated. Antimicrobial properties of complexes 1-4 have also been evaluated.

Schiff base metal complexes have been a widely studied subject because of their industrial and biological applications^{1,2}. Studies of new kind of (chemotherapeutic) Schiff bases are now attracting the attention of biochemists^{3,4}. The literature survey revealed that a systematic study is further required on this subject⁵⁻⁸. The present study deals with the structural aspects of some Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes involving bioactive ligands.

Results and Discussion

The analytical and physical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the Schiff bases and their metal complexes*

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Metal %: Found/(Calcd.)
FIZ	Green	180	-
FAAP	Orange	205	-
FAP	Brown	115	-
[Ni(FIZ) ₂]Cl ₂ (1)	Yellow	250	10.22 (10.44)
[Cu(FIZ) ₂]Cl ₂ (2)	Green	240	10.99 (11.24)
[Ni(FAAP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]Cl ₂ (3)	Brown	240	7.83 (8.04)
[Cu(FAAP)Cl ₂]·H ₂ O (4)	Brown	220	14.40 (14.64)
[Ni(FAP) ₂]Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O (5)	Yellow	145	11.23 (11.43)
[Cu(FAP) ₂]Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O (6)	Brown	160	12.51 (12.73)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with FIZ: The molar conductance data suggest the Ni^{II} complex (176.4 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) to be 1 : 2 electrolyte and the Cu^{II} complex (28.2 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) to be a non-electrolyte⁹. The Ni^{II} complex is diamagnetic while the Cu^{II} complex is paramagnetic (1.92 B.M.).

The sharp ir ligand band at 1620 cm⁻¹ (C=N azomethine group) shifted to 1570 cm⁻¹ in complexes 1 and 2. This shift refers to the coordination through azomethine nitrogen¹⁰. The ligand band at 1650 cm⁻¹ (C=O) shifted to higher side on complexation and appeared

at 1680 ± 10 cm⁻¹ in 1 and 2. This shift has been assigned for the bonding of FIZ to the metal through carbonyl group. The cause of this positive shift may lie in the competitive inductive effect or high mesomeric interaction in the complex where adjacent groups supply an electron drift and which is probably activated by the presence of the metal ion¹⁰⁻¹³. The pyridine ring vibrations due to tertiary nitrogen at 1470 and 1030 cm⁻¹ in the ligand remained unchanged after complexation, which reflect its non-involvement with the metal ion. A medium sharp band due to C-O-C stretching of furan appeared at 1210 ± 10 cm⁻¹ in the ligand¹⁰⁻¹⁴. Its non-involvement in chelation has been inferred on the basis of no change in its position and shape.

The presence of lattice water in the spectrum of only Cu^{II} complex has been inferred on the basis of a broad band at 3400 cm⁻¹ (OH). The new medium band at 420 ± 10 cm⁻¹ in these complexes has been assigned to ν_{M-N} mode. The ν_{M-O} band appeared at 470 and 510 cm⁻¹ in the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes respectively. In the Cu^{II} complex, another weak band appeared at 350 cm⁻¹ (M-Cl)^{10,14}.

The electronic spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex showing two intense bands at 13157 and 23809 cm⁻¹ and relatively weak band at 19607 cm⁻¹ have tentatively been assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_g(ν₁), ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{2g}(ν₂) and ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g}(ν₃) transitions respectively^{15,16}, which suggests a square-planar geometry. The Cu^{II} complex showed a broad band at 17543-13872 cm⁻¹, which is attributed to ²E_g → ²T_{2g} transition favouring a distorted octahedral geometry. The ligand field parameters, viz. 10 Dq, λ, LFSE for 2 are calculated to be 16319 cm⁻¹, (-) 660 cm⁻¹ and 117.4 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively^{13,15,16}.

The esr spectrum of the Cu^{II} complex exhibited Lorentzian type of peaks. The values of esr parameters, viz. g_{||}, g_⊥, g_{av}, G and Δg are calculated to be 2.11316, 2.06439, 2.08064, 1.75742 and 0.04877 respectively. The value of g_{||} (2.11316) indicates the prevalent covalent character to the metal-ligand band, which suggests the interaction between

the two copper centers in solid state and the medium to strong field nature of the coordinated ligand. The correlation $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > 2$ suggests a tetragonally elongated or square-planar structure with the ground state $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with FAAP: The molar conductance (in methanol) data of the FAAP complexes suggest that the Ni^{II} complex (**3**, 165.8 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) is 1 : 2 electrolyte and the Cu^{II} complex (**4**, 34.0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) is non-ionic in nature⁹. The observed magnetic moment values are 3.08 and 1.82 B.M. for the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes respectively.

The ir ligand (FAAP) band at 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N) shifted to lower wavenumber at 1580 $\pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in complexes **3** and **4**, owing to coordination through azomethine nitrogen^{10,11}. The ligand band at 1670 cm^{-1} (C=O) shifted in the metal chelates and appeared¹⁹ at 1630 $\pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This indicates that azomethine and carbonyl groups of FAAP are involved in coordination. The characteristic C–O–C bands of furan (1250 and 1080 cm^{-1}) in the ligand, remained unchanged in the complexes, ruling out the possibility of coordination through the oxygen of furan ring. The spectra of the complexes showed a broad band around 3400 cm^{-1} (OH). The presence of coordinated water in the Ni^{II} complex has been inferred on the basis of a medium intensity band at 740 cm^{-1} (OH-rocking). The new bands at 480 ± 10 and 430 $\pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have respectively been assigned for $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ in the complexes. An additional weak band appeared at 350 cm^{-1} (M–Cl) in the Cu^{II} complex^{6,8,10}.

The electronic spectrum of **3** exhibited three bands, viz. 11904 (ν_1), a split shoulders at 14492 and 19231 (ν_2) and 28571 cm^{-1} (ν_3) which correspond to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively. The split in the second band (ν_2) may be due to spin-orbit coupling and lowering of symmetry¹³⁻¹⁶. A distorted octahedral geometry has been suggested for this complex. The ligand field parameters, viz. 10 Dq , B , β , β^0 , λ' and LFSE are calculated to be 11904 cm^{-1} , 637 cm^{-1} , 0.68, 38.75, (-)269 cm^{-1} and 170.99 kJ mol^{-1} respectively. Complex **4** exhibited bands at 14084 and 18181 cm^{-1} , which are attributed to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions and accordingly square-planar geometry has been suggested^{15,16}.

Complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with FAP: The molar conductance data in methanol of the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}-FAP complexes fall in the range 196–207 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, and suggest them as $[\text{Ni}(\text{FAP})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**5**) and $[\text{Cu}(\text{FAP})_2]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (**6**). Complex **5** is diamagnetic while **6** is paramagnetic having a magnetic moment of 1.84 B.M.

A strong ir band at 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N, azomethine) of FAP shifted to lower wavenumber at 1570 ± 10 in complexes **5** and **6**, suggesting the coordination through azomethine nitrogen^{5,6,10}. Shifting of a medium intensity ligand band at 1210 cm^{-1} (C–O–C of furan ring) to 1160 $\pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes suggests the coordination

through the ring oxygen^{20,21}. Pyridine ring vibrations remained unchanged in the complexes, negating the possibility of coordination of pyridine ring nitrogen, as the chelation through furan oxygen results a more stable five-membered ring structure than that through pyridine nitrogen^{7,8,20,21}. The presence of lattice water in both the complexes has been inferred owing to the appearance of a hump around 3430 cm^{-1} (OH). The two new bands were observed in the complexes at 430 ± 10 (M–N) and 480 $\pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (M–O)^{10,20,21}.

In the electronic spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex, three bands at 12987 (weaker), 19607 and 26315 cm^{-1} have tentatively been assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ (ν_1), ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$ (ν_2) and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ (ν_3) transitions respectively, proving the square-planar geometry of **5**. Two bands of the Cu^{II} complex at 13157 and 19230 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow 2E_g$ transitions. This is in accordance with the square-planar geometry.

Antimicrobial activity: Antibacterial and antifungal activities of complexes **1-4** and the Schiff bases were studied against *B. subtilis*, *E. coli*, *A. fumigatus* and *A. niger* at 50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration by single disc method^{22,23} using streptomycin as control. Against all the organisms, ligands FIZ and FAAP did not exhibit any remarkable activity (zone of inhibition <5 mm), whereas all the complexes showed moderate activities (zone of inhibition 8–18 mm). The activity was found to increase in the order, Cu^{II}-FIZ > Ni^{II}-FIZ > Cu^{II}-FAAP > Ni^{II}-FAAP. It is suggested that the compounds having antimicrobial activity may act either by killing the microbe or by inhibiting multiplication of the microbe by blocking their active sites^{3,22,23}.

Experimental

The Schiff bases (FIZ, FAAP and FAP) were synthesised by refluxing a mixture of an equimolar amount of 2-furfuraldehyde with isoniazide/4-aminoantipyrine/2-aminopyridine in methanolic medium on a water-bath for 3–6 h. The resulting products were crystallised from methanol.

The metal complexes (**1-6**) were prepared by adding a methanolic solution of the respective metal salt ($\text{MCl}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$) to a methanolic solution of the Schiff base (FIZ, FAAP or FAP) in 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio and refluxing the mixture on a hot water-bath for 4–6 h. The coloured precipitate that appeared on cooling the solution was washed with methanol and petroleum ether successively. It was crystallised and dried over anhydrous CaCl_2 under reduced pressure and then in an electric oven at 70 $^\circ$.

M.p. was determined on a Toshniwal CL-0301 apparatus. Electronic spectra (MeOH) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer-Lambda-2B spectrophotometer. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. ESR spectrum (solid state) were recorded at 30 $^\circ$ on the X-band at 9.5 GHz under magnetic field strength of 4000 \pm 2000 gauss. Magnetic moment was measured at room temperature by the

Gouy's technique. Conductance was measured on an Elico-CM-82 conductivity bridge. The purity of the compounds was monitored by tlc using silica gel.

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